

	Bibliography New	Positions/Job offers	Questionnaire	Interviews	Edison project
Bibliography Old (60 key phrases)	curation data curation data curation education data curation profiles data management data quality digital curation digital preservation e-science professionals large scale information management problems metadata plurality of curation roles preservation repositories research data research data curation research data management	curation data curation data management digital curation digital preservation preservation research data research data curation research data management	curation data curation data management data quality data sharing data stewardship digital curation digital preservation preservation repositories research data research data management	area of data curation data curation data management data management plan digital curation metadata research data research data management	curation data curation data management data quality

	Positions/Job offers	Questionnaire	Interviews	Edison project
Bibliography New (69 key phrases)	curation data curation data management data management planning digital curation digital preservation preservation research data research data curation research data management	curation data curation data management data management planning data quality digital curation digital preservation information management preservation repositories research data research data management research data services	curation curators data curation data management digital curation metadata research data research data management	curation data curation data management data quality data science

	Questionnaire	Interviews	Edison project
Positions (40 key phrases)	curation data curation data management data management planning digital curation digital preservation preservation research data research data management	curation data curation data management digital curation research data research data management scholarly communication	curation data curation data management

	Interviews	Edison project
Questionnaire (56 key phrases)	curation data curation data management digital curation research data research data management	curation data curation data management data quality

	Edison project
Interviews (34 key phrases)	curation data curation data management